

ALL-Ready Project Deliverable 2.5

ALL-Ready – The European Agroecology
Living Lab and Research Infrastructure Network: preparation phase

.....

Agroecology Open Innovation: Best cases across Europe

.....

Deliverable Number	D2.5
Work Package	WP2
Deliverable type	Report
Dissemination level	Public
Deliverable leader	INRAE
Due date	31 January 2022 (V1)
Submission date	17 February 2022
Version	V2 – V1 approved
Authors (contact)	Bastian Gödel (bastian.godel@inrae.fr)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101000349 (ALL-Ready).

Disclaimer

The information and views set out in this deliverable are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union. Neither the European Union institutions and bodies nor any person acting on their behalf may be held responsible for the use which may be made of the information contained therein.

Table of Contents

1. INTRODUCTION	4
1.1 DESCRIPTION OF THE DELIVERABLE	4
2. METHODOLOGY	4
2.1 THE QUESTIONNAIRE EXPLAINED	4
2.2 ANALYSIS OF THE QUESTIONNAIRE	5
3. DESCRIPTION OF 'BEST CASE' EXAMPLES	5
3.1 INITIATIVE 1: ECO-FARM SOSNÓWKA, LUBLIN, POLAND	6
3.2 INITIATIVE 2: DEPARTMENT OF ORGANIC FARMING AND CROPPING SYSTEMS, UNIVERSITY OF KASSEL, GERMANY	6
3.3 INITIATIVE 3: AMERICAN FARM SCHOOL, THESSALONIKI, GREECE.....	7
3.4 INITIATIVE 4: CARBONFARM - INNOVATION CENTRE FOR ORGANIC FARMING, AARHUS, DENMARK 8	8
3.5 INITIATIVE 5: MENTER A BUSNES, ABERYSTWYTH, WALES.....	9
4. PROBLEMS DURING THE WORK PROCESS AND RECOMMENDATIONS	10
4.1 UNCERTAINTIES AND DIFFICULTIES OF THE DELIVERABLE	10
4.2 THE FUTURE OF THE DELIVERABLE	10
5. CONCLUSIONS	11
6. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	11

List of abbreviations

AE	Agroecology
EC	European Commission
ENoLL	European Network of Living Labs
EU	European Union
LL	Living Lab (Laboratory)
NCP	National Contact Point
OIA	Open Innovation Arrangement
RI	Research Infrastructure
SCAR	Standing Committee on Agricultural Research
VRE	Virtual Research Environment
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

ALL-Ready is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) funded by the European Commission (EC) with the aim of preparing a framework for a future European network of Living Labs (LL) and Research Infrastructures (RI) that will enable the transition towards agroecology throughout Europe. Based on the premise that agroecology can strengthen the sustainability and resilience of farming systems, the project will contribute to addressing the multiple challenges that they are facing today including climate change, loss of biodiversity, dwindling resources, degradation of soil and water quality.

1.1 Description of the Deliverable

This task evaluates the mapped regulatory drivers of AE initiatives that have been identified through an online questionnaire (link: [Questionnaire](#)) developed in WP2. This exercise involved, as a first step, the extension of the geographically sensitive indicators and definitions of agroecological LLs and the support of RIs or other OIAs developed in WP1 (D1.1 and mainly D.1.2). The results of the questionnaire helped us to rank these organisations based on the developed score on their maturity within the process of AE transition. In total, we picked five initiatives (at least one LL, one RI and one OIA within different countries) with the highest scores and described them as 'best cases and practices' of AE transition across Europe.

2. Methodology

The online survey tool is based on the developed questionnaire which operationalises the inclusion criteria described in D1.2. The questionnaire simplifies the criteria to ensure comprehension by participants who are not fully familiar with the concept of agroecology transition. Here, the questionnaire makes it possible to situate responding organisations within the transition process, and identify 'best case' examples. The organisations thus identified through the questionnaire had been further investigated e.g. for the analysis of the value added of a European Network of LLs and RIs in WP4 and as (potential) candidates of the pilot network in WP3.

2.1 The Questionnaire Explained

The online tool combines open and closed questions. Closed questions enable the project to understand if a specific organisation is fulfilling the criteria of agroecology transition based on our definitions (WP1), and to what extent. The open questions enable us to collect in-depth information, and to gather examples; these questions are screening the main activities depicted in *Figure 1*. Both types of questions, open and closed, were used to rank and pick the best cases for this deliverable. A more detailed overall explanation of the questionnaire and how it is linked to various work packages and deliverables can be found in D2.1, while the background of the questionnaire can be found in D1.2.

For this deliverable 2.5, three main aspects were of major importance. First, we structured the questions based on what we consider are elementary criteria and activities of AE transition that should be fulfilled (e.g. criteria: co-creation, resilience, climate adaptation etc., *see Figure 1*). These first (closed) questions per criterion are always binary and rather general. For instance, 'is your initiative working with others to create knowledge and/or innovation?' Second, several more detailed questions about the same criterion follow. Here, the possible answers were structured in a classified way, meaning that the choice of each specific answer

was supposed to give us certain insights into the maturity of the initiative within the transition process for each of the specific criteria – for instance, if an initiative is leading an activity, participating, just thinking about it for the future or not at all interested (see below). Third, each of the five answer possibilities received a specific score that helped as to rank the initiatives based in their answers.

2.2 Analysis of the Questionnaire

After the assessment of how to evaluate the answers and transfer them into a specific scoring system, we decided on the following scoring for these chosen answers: 'yes, we are leading this activity' (4 points); 'yes, we participate in this activity' (3 points); 'no, but we plan to do soon in the future' (2 points); 'no, but we would like to some when' (1 point); 'no' (0 points). For the 'best cases' we chose the initiatives with the highest overall scores. At the same time we ensured that no relevant inclusion criteria identified in D2.1 were ignored within the top initiatives (e.g. high overall score, but missing xy criterion completely, or, initiatives self-defining as LL, but ignoring major relevant LL definitions were not chosen).

The questionnaire was and still is distributed amongst the agroecology-related initiatives that have been identified by NCPs during the phase 1 mapping survey, the pilot network members (WP3), on regional workshops of WP2 (*reports about each workshop are going to be prepared until January/February*) and through other sources and contacts (e.g. SCAR working group, ENOLL, etc.).

Figure 1: AE activities that foster the transition process

3. Description of 'Best Case' Examples

In total 56 initiatives (until the 19th December, 2022), so far, filled in the questionnaire completely (while several more only parts of it, and thus have been ignored for this deliverable). A closer description of the overview and diversity amongst all the investigated initiatives in terms of maturity and distribution across Europe can be found in D2.4. In total, 56 closed detailed questions were asked, making it possible to reach 224 'points' in total. The five best cases chosen all achieved results above 200 in our scoring system.

3.1 Initiative 1: ECO-FARM Sosnówka, Lublin, Poland

The first initiative chosen we considered as a relevant candidate for 'best cases', is Lubelskie Herbs from Poland. They function as an innovative model of herb production in the agroforestry system including the production, processing and distribution of herbs in the Zielawa Valley, Poland. The initiative is participating in several projects with the aim of creating sustainable systems that ensure economic and ecological profitability.

In our questionnaire, this initiative stated that they lead several activities to create knowledge and innovation including several types of stakeholders. For instance, they established and coordinate the 'Agroforestry Cluster' which is a platform to learn, exchange, experience and start agroecology business cooperation between entrepreneurs and farmers, and implement agroecology models of production (agro and food production). The Cluster members are: farmers, entrepreneurs, academics, NGOs, innovation brokers, agricultural advisors and others. The 'Cluster' runs several innovation projects each year. It includes conducting research and experimentation using different data sources. Each year the initiative delivers ~50 education programs with 300 - 500 participants. All educational programs are delivered in real life context on farms implementing agroecology practices. Further, they cooperate with several academic institutions and leading agroforestry research, such as implementation projects in agroforestry (agroecology model). In cooperation with IT companies they developed digital tools for management of agroecology farming processes as well as a digital tool to provide food passports for agroecology products. ECO-FARM also promotes resilience and sustainability along the food value chain. They developed a model of carbon neutral production which is implemented by farmers and entrepreneurs. They help organisations along the value chain to become more resilient and adaptive to changing environmental conditions due to climate change, through teaching and implementation of agroforestry practices (farmers) and establishing sustainable cooperation (farmers and entrepreneurs along food chain production). Moreover, they lead several activities that support diversity. Here, the organisation is involved in making land use more diverse at all scales by implementing different agroforestry and agroecology practices, taking into account local and regional differences. They promote polycultures, alley cropping and mixtures of them as farm management practices, they protect biodiversity, and successfully introduced several wild plants including endangered species into the cultivations. Further, they teach innovative bee keeping as well as how to design and implement different agroforestry systems on the farm. ECO-FARM promotes synergies between different ecosystem functions and the efficiency in the use of natural resources. For instance, they encourage agroforestry systems by using inter-cropping, mulch and soil cover plants in order to reduce evaporation. They developed vertical agro-photovoltaic systems which reduce water usage and energy, and increase yield at the same time. The initiative is also leading related activities to create circular and solidarity economies by supporting short and regional value chains that are environmentally friendly and create new, local jobs. Further they developed a tool that is enabling users of value chains to follow the product from farm to shop. Finally, they described themselves as functioning as both a RI and LL at once.

3.2 Initiative 2: Department of Organic Farming and Cropping Systems, University of Kassel, Germany

The Department of Organic Farming and Cropping Systems investigates how productivity in cropping systems can be increased while simultaneously improving ecosystem services, via using biological processes. Research areas include optimising cropping systems, measures to increase soil fertility including composting techniques, root ecology and root-soil interactions, diversification of cropping systems e.g. via mixed cropping and agroforestry, and integration of nature conservation measures in agroecosystems. Furthermore, inter- and transdisciplinary topics such as environmental effects of organic farming especially with

respect to ground water and nature protection, and quantifying societal impact of practice-oriented research are covered. They lead several activities that create knowledge and innovation. Their research ideas are developed together with farmers and then researched on-farm, for example on nitrogen management under cover crops. For instance, they lead projects for optimizing processes of clover grass composting, combined with other alternatives of clover grass utilization for organic farms without animals, including economic analyses, on-farm research related to nitrate leaching in chicken paddocks and several projects related to social farming in the region. The initiative cooperates in the field of agroforestry between Hessian universities, an agroforestry consulting company in the region, the LLH (Hessian practice consulting) and practical farms with agroforestry systems installed. They conduct research in biodynamic vineyards in France and on-farm research in market gardening farms. Additionally, the department promotes resilience and sustainability. The main areas of research, root growth and composting, have been followed for more than a decade and will be continued. They work on long-term field trials which compare different crop rotations and fertilization strategies for organic farms with and without animals, and will be installed for agroforestry. The initiative further leads many activities that support diversity as it is considered to be essential for efficient crop production. Their own organic experimental farm uses crop rotation with legume-grass mixtures, cereals, potatoes and field vegetables, and installed several structural elements (hedges, fruit trees, flowering strips) in the region ten years ago. Additionally, a milking cow herd has been built up resulting in land-use change from arable land to grasslands which was associated with an increase in species diversity of plants, insects and birds. Increases in diversity and abundance of several animal groups e.g. field hares, small mammals and birds have been documented. Further, diversification is planned with agroforestry systems and introduction of medicinal plants. An organic vegetable self-harvesting area for >100 families/people from the region has been installed as a result of a research project and adds further diversity to the experimental farm. They foster climate change mitigation and promote environmental adaptation of agricultural practices. This is done through activities related to increasing biodiversity: they mentioned already having observed an increase of pollinators since the conversion to organic farming associated with introducing grazing animals on the farm and nature conservation measures such as hedges, segetal plants growing amongst crops and flowering strips. Carbon sequestration is achieved e.g. by growing perennial fodder crops, trees and hedges (for nature conservation resulting from a large project ten years ago, and in agroforestry systems planned to be installed this year). Another important aim of the initiative is to promote synergies between the different ecosystem functions. Synergies between different ecological processes are achieved e.g. by combining dairy cows and arable cropping using legume-grass mixtures as fodder and simultaneously for introducing N to the system and humus build-up. Another important aspect is the efficient use of natural resources, e.g. through the reduction of consumption of energy by using photovoltaics and wood-based heating. They also cooperate with a biogas plant that generates energy from cow dung, and use wood for heating. Finally, they are involved in circular and solidarity economies by operating an organic food store where also products from other farms in the region are sold, and all workers are employed under fair conditions. Just as for ECO-FARM, the department of Organic Farming and Cropping Systems fulfils and describes themselves as both a RI and LL at the same time.

3.3 Initiative 3: American Farm School, Thessaloniki, Greece

The next initiative represents the American Farm School located in Thessaloniki, Greece. The first main role is their leadership in different activities that create innovation and knowledge through co-creation. They use agro-food clusters, underpinned by private open telecommunication networks, for instance, to support local wine grape producers to determine the terroir characteristics (including microbial biodiversity) that determine the attributes of different wines. The organisation promotes resilience and sustainability by

leading various activities, e.g. helping other organisations along the value chain to become more resilient and adaptive to changing environmental conditions due to climate change. For instance, they create short supply chains for free range indigenous cattle frameworks, and combine environmental sustainability through pasture management with financial viability of small animal farmers and digitally assisted traceability. The Farm School also promotes diversity in terms of land use, on-farm practices, involved actors and cultivars. For example, they support local farmers in the Peloponnese region to promote local tomato varieties and collaborate with high-end holiday resorts that are interested in the local products. Climate change mitigation is encouraged through monitoring and management of the CO₂ footprint of suppliers of the whole supermarket chain. They are involved in different EIP AGRI Operational Groups and support synergies between ecosystem functions (e.g. in agroecosystems with free ranging animals and plant cultivations) with the aim to increase resilience through environmental management. They are not yet involved in producing non-crop plants to enhance biodiversity, but plan to do so in the future. To increase the efficiency and responsible use of natural resources, the initiative utilises microbial bio-stimulants in a number of cooperatives to enhance soil health and reduce water usage. Nevertheless, while carbon farming or recycling of biomass and organic matter are on the agenda, they not yet practiced outside of the on-campus vertically demonstration farm, where recycling of water and piloting manure solutions are conducted. Last, the initiative is working with socially disadvantaged ethnic groups of producers in the region of Eastern Macedonia on the introduction of stevia cultivation to encourage circular economy and social justice. Further, they support the cultivation of tea and the promotion of provenance and producer identity in mountain animal farming. The Farm school does not see themselves as a LL or RI, but as some different type of OIA that fosters the AE transition process.

3.4 Initiative 4: Carbonfarm - Innovation Centre for Organic Farming, Aarhus, Denmark

The fourth initiative is the Innovation Centre for Organic Farming (Carbonfarm). It functions as a centre for the development of organic farming in Denmark and considers themselves as a LL. Through research, trials, the collection and dissemination of knowledge about agriculture, the Innovation Centre tries to ensure that organic farming develops according to organic principles and the UN's 17 Sustainable Development Goals. The objective is to foster a more sustainable agriculture including the reduction of the climate footprint within Denmark, to become climate-neutral by 2050, and to promote the development for the benefit of the agricultural sector on a technically, economically and environmentally optimised basis, in accordance with good research practices. It was established in 2021 as an independent non-profit company by Organic Denmark and the Danish Agriculture & Food Council.

The Centre is leading various activities to create knowledge and innovation. For instance, they connect with farmers and invite different groups of stakeholders to their events to make sure each group will be heard. Very important for them is that the innovation and knowledge creation is done in a real-life context, using a diversity of data sources and methods, so potential users can profit from the outcomes in their daily life. Another goal of the initiative is to promote resilience. This can be achieved by focusing on agroecosystems to become more resilient to climate change and its linked disturbances (e.g. extreme weathers). They also try to support other organisations along the value chain to overcome these obstacles while considering the economic impacts of the transition process. So far, a long-term strategy for a resilient agriculture is missing, but existing as a plan for the future years. The Innovation Centre is also involved in the diversification of land use at different scales (field, landscape, region), from different practices (crop, livestock, energy etc.) to the involvement of various actors and stakeholders throughout the value chain. Furthermore, the organisation

promotes the use of products adapted to local conditions and diets, as well as the protection of biodiversity as a main objective. The next important aspect is the adaptation to climate and environmental changes through corresponding agricultural practices. These can be activities related to integrated pest management, usage of perennial and cover crops or the reduction of tillage use. The organisation also aims to promote low-input farming (water usage, nutrients, pesticides), the protection of domestic pollinators and animal welfare in general. To promote synergies between different functions of the agroecosystem is another objective of the Centre. All the activities should be connected and influence wider societal and ecological processes to accelerate the transition through the practices of agroforestry, rotational grazing and integrated crop-livestock systems. Although the reduce of water consumption is not a priority, the efficiency of natural resources is a top issue on the list as well. The initiative promotes the reduced application of pesticides, veterinary drugs for animals, energy use as well as drugs and fertilisers. On the other hand, recycling of biomass and organic matter for energy generation is pushed forward. To encourage a local and circular economy, the Innovation Centre is supporting the food production in a way that generates an added value for the region and shortens the value chain as much as possible by also encouraging demands for seasonal and regional products. Nevertheless, there is still a lack in the creation of 'fair paid' jobs within the agricultural sector that the Centre aims to improve in the future. A similar plan exists for the support of gender equality as well as the support of values (equity, dignity, inclusion), food sovereignty and activities to ensure the maintenance of culturally appropriate food traditions within the regions.

3.5 Initiative 5: Menter a Busnes, Aberystwyth, Wales

Menter a Busnes is an independent, not for profit company that supports individuals, businesses and organisations in Wales to start and develop their business, mainly related to innovation and agricultural practices. They are providing consultancy services on economic development issues, entrepreneurship awareness, business start-up and business growth support to individuals and groups in Wales and beyond. They have developed and worked in several projects with the aim to provide one-to-one support, guidance and training for farmers and forestry businesses in Wales, supporting Welsh food and drink producers to grow through the development of new products and markets, or encourage people from practical and scientific backgrounds to work together to solve common agricultural and forestry problems, with the use of new and sustainable technologies.

Within their agricultural projects the initiative attaches great importance to create knowledge and innovation by connecting with farmers and bring together different groups of stakeholders. Often these events are organised by the initiative itself and happen in real-life context. By that, they are actively bringing together people with different expertise which creates opportunities to draw from different experiences, introduce new ideas and use the latest knowledge to tackle problems. The role of Menter a Busnes is also to share the results with the industry so others can also benefit from these projects. To promote resilience and sustainability, the organisation provides support and advice to farmers on a wide variety of topics including transitioning to new ways of working in agroecology and climate change adaptation. So far, the resilience could not be upscaled to include the whole value chain, but it can be considered as an ambitious aim for the future. Another goal is to support diversity. They are involved in the process to increase the diversity of land-use by e.g. introducing new, diverse practices to farmers for crop production and livestock farming. No focus is laying on the diversity of cultivars, seeds and breeds, but instead on the involvement of various value chain actors or diverse products from regional production. Further, the protection of biodiversity and usage of agroecological practices (e.g. crop rotation) has a high value within the organisation's projects. They try to encourage farmers to adopt new grassland management techniques including rotational grazing, how to reduce reliance on chemical fertilisers, improving grass utilisation, animal welfare and to protect domestic

pollinators. For instance, in one project the involved farmers, together with representatives from the Bumblebee Conservation Trust, created useful resources for other farmers (also a booklet) who are interested in improving areas of their farms to provide good habitat for pollinating insects. On demonstration farms the initiative tries to highlight the benefits of trees and hedgerows to farming infrastructure and to create synergies between different functions of the agroecosystem. Agroforestry, rotational grazing and integrated crop-livestock systems are just a few more important aspects for the company to be highlighted as well. The initiative promotes the efficient use of natural resources such as the reduced application of fertilisers or the reduction of water consumption. In detail, they for instance provide access to infrastructure clinics so that farmers can receive guidance on how to manage farm buildings to reduce water collection in slurry pits, to only name one example. In one project they promoted to use alternative soil and agronomic inputs, and practices such as green manure and composting to improve soil structure and reduce reliance on chemical fertilisers and. The efficient and responsible usage of resources is a high and important position of the organisation, from soil input to water and energy usage, recycling and greenhouse gas reduction. Moreover, the initiative supports food production within the region to keep value chains short, and tries to increase the value of local and seasonal products through 'fair' jobs within the agricultural sector and socio-ecological justice. Finally, Menter a Busnes tries to help food businesses in Wales to become more sustainable and profitable, but also fostering inclusive practices and encourages diverse ethics within the sector as well as food sovereignty, gender equality, the support of traditional foods and diets and the participation of vulnerable and disadvantaged groups throughout the value chain.

4. Problems during the work process and recommendations

4.1 Uncertainties and Difficulties of the Deliverable

During the work on this deliverable, several uncertainties and problems crossed our way. First, the creation of the questionnaire from the work in D1.2 took much longer than expected. When trying the first initial versions (e.g. within the pilot network or within the consortium of the project), it became clear that the language of the questions was too complicated and abstract for people not strongly involved in the AE transition concept. Hence, it was necessary to simplify the language and make the whole survey more straight-forward and clearer. The second problem was and still is the low number of responses that we received. Although we sent the questionnaire to a large number of people and initiatives and also hoped to gain even more answers through snow-balling effects, the number of answers has remained rather low. This might be again related to several aspects. On one hand, people (especially when reaching out to the wrong person within an initiative) might still not have fully understood many of the questions and definitions, hence ignored us. On the other hand, the questionnaire is rather long and time-consuming (thus with necessary information for the project). In general, possible participants, especially when being busy and contacted through emails, are often not very motivated to fill in an online survey completely. Finally, NCPs that have been already contacted previously or even done an interview for WP2, might have showed less effort to spread our questionnaire accordingly.

4.2 The Future of The Deliverable

In general, this document could be seen as a starting point to collect information across Europe, but could also be improved and expanded over time (even after All-Ready for a publication or similar). The online questionnaire will remain open and we are trying to catch

every possibility to further spread it whenever there is a chance that promising or relevant initiatives could fill it in. Furthermore, four more regional workshops in relation to WP4 are planned for early spring. During these workshops, that are planned to take place in all four regions of Europe (one each in the south, north, west and central-east), we are planning to work with people who are involved in AE initiatives such as LLs and RIs and so-called networks of networks (e.g. European projects, JPIs, networks of LLs etc.). Through face-to-face work on a co-creation base, we are expecting to receive many new insights from regional initiatives that are very difficult to gain through online searches or even surveys (such as ours). Nevertheless, these workshops might also be a good opportunity to explain and promote our questionnaire again (and the future network and partnership) as already done during the first set of regional workshops, so that more involved people might fill it in and provide us with additional, relevant and valuable information. We also plan to include several of the results from the questionnaire (including the ones described in this deliverable) into the Virtual Research Environment (VRE) of WP6. This might be a chance to illustrate the results in an interactive and visual way beside this written document. Furthermore, several of the results might be used for a publication in collaboration with WP4 as several of the answers received should give us a better overview of what is needed for the governance and added value of a future network of LLs and RIs.

5. Conclusions

Altogether, there are some examples across Europe that show that AE transition is possible. We have identified several initiatives that use identified, valuable practices that are essential for the transition process. We have described three relevant initiatives here to explain how and in which way they are fulfilling specific, elementary criteria, from co-creation to climate change mitigation and from protection of biodiversity to the involvement of various stakeholders along the whole value chain. For the future, it would not only be important that more and more initiatives are encouraged in agroecology transition, but also that existing ones get in contact, learn from each other, build networks, partnerships and 'networks of networks' to spread the knowledge and experiences as wide and effectively as possible. Until now, we do not know enough about to what extent the development of such initiatives is flourishing across Europe. By spreading our questionnaire we are hoping to contribute to existing knowledge of relevant organisations across Europe. Furthermore, by outlining some initiatives as 'best cases', we pinpoint which criteria and practices could/should be tackled (as an example) by an initiative that is willing to follow the aim to foster AE transition.

6. Acknowledgements

We thank the partners of ALL-Ready for their critical exchange, input and remarks of this deliverable and their comments to improve it.